

WAYS OF INCREASING THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF BEEKEEPING IN AGRICULTURE

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Abstract. *The given article analyzes the cost structure, profitability and net profit of beekeeping and their change in accordance with a change in the approach to the production of additional types of beekeeping products, that is, diversification of production areas.*

Keywords: *plants, external pollination, bees, harvest, alfalfa, legumes, sunflower, fruit trees, polycultures, cotton fields.*

Introduction. It is important to suggest that analyzing the domestic and foreign markets for beekeeping products, it should be noted that according to the network of beekeepers in the Republic of Uzbekistan, 25.1 thousand bee families are produced annually. Per capita honey consumption in Uzbekistan has reached 700 grams per year, which is comparable to the European level.

Agriculture is one of the largest industries in Uzbekistan. The population exceeds 36 million people, which causes the existence of many social problems associated with the abundance of labor resources and employment of the population. Agriculture is one of the main activities of the population living in the region.

Definitely, the presence of colorful landscapes with diverse flora allows residents to engage in beekeeping, which is an additional, and sometimes the main source of income in the economy. According to the society of beekeepers in agriculture, more than 2.5 thousand households and up to 50 families are engaged in beekeeping. But there are also large bee farms with up to 400 bee families in their farms. The difference between beekeeping and other industries is that it requires relatively small investment capital and labor force, which allows for self-employment of the population.

Initially, beekeeping was aimed at satisfying the need for honey consumption, later it became a source of income and the most important type of agricultural production, which clearly shows the relevance of the problem of beekeeping development.

The beekeeping industry has two obvious positive features:

- creation of bee products that are valuable for health and in demand on the market: bee venom, bee bread and propolis;

- as well as socio-economic significance - employment and source of income for most of the rural population. Unfortunately, one of the most important advantages of this sector is the plant pollination service, which is not included in the market chains for determining the price of the final product, the economic value of beekeepers' services is poorly reflected or is practically zero, due to that, it cannot fully reveal its development potential.

The main conclusion of the analysis and the project and the main content of the further development of beekeeping is the idea of diversification of beekeeping products, that beekeepers should not neglect additional sources of income from auxiliary beekeeping products, that is, the production of bee bags, royal jelly and bee venom. Such diversification leads to a significant increase in the profitability of beekeeping farms, therefore, to the sustainability of beekeeping

farms, an increase in their competitiveness and, in particular, to an increase in the volume of the related service - pollination, which increases the profitability of crop production as a whole.

The main material for the analysis was information obtained from beekeepers during personal conversations. In addition to this data, prices for beekeeping products on the local market were used.

The cost-benefit analysis used the number of 22 practicing beekeepers participating in the project. Each of them has from 50 to 100 nests in their personal farm. We conditionally divided them into 3 groups.

Table 1

Project farms by the number of bee colonies

Farms with hives	Number of farms	Sell only honey	Sales Honey + propolis + queen cells + bags
0-100	18	18	0
101-250	3	0	3
250+	1	-	1
Total	22	18	4

A simple categorization already provides information on success indicators. As can be seen from the table, all large beekeeping farms use all types of income generation, while small farms focus only on honey sales. The question of whether the diversification of income sources will lead to success and, as a result, to an increase in the size of farms is a matter of consideration. In our opinion, this is an absolute factor and an indicator of the correctness of the conclusions presented in the analysis.

The following indicators are used to analyze 100 cells:

The cost of products obtained as a result of beekeeping activities - Gross beekeeping product (GDP)

Total costs = Total variable costs + Fixed costs;

Net profit = GNP;

Relative profit, profitability = GDP /GNP

Calculations are made for 10 frame nests, which are considered one family.

The average yield of one family in the 2022 season was 10-12 kg of honey. A more conservative figure of 10 kg was taken for the calculations.

Based on this, the amount of honey obtained per 100 hives is about 1000 kg. At a wholesale purchase price of 1 kg of honey of 100,000 sums, the total gross product of the beekeeper from honey (GDP 1) will be 100,000,000 (one hundred million) soums or 8,734 US dollars.

Below is information on beekeeping expenses. The gradation to variables and constants is conditional.

Here is some information on variable costs:

Table 2

Variable Costs in Beekeeping

№	Variable Cost Category	For one slot	100 per slot.	US Dollar
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1.	grams in sugar amount	14 kg sugar * 14 000 s u m = 196 000	19 600 000 sum	1712 Dollar
2.	Transportation costs	60 000 sum	6 000 000 sum	524 Dollar
3.	Labor hired during migration	24 000 sum	2 400 000 sum	210 Dollar
4.	Field rent	20 000 sum	2 000 000 sum	175 Dollar
5.	Beekeeper's living expenses in beekeeping	16 000 sum	1 600 000 sum	140 Dollar
6.	Redemption of families (colonies)		3 000 000 sum	262 Dollar
7.	Purchase of queen cells for raising queens	9 000 sum	900 000 sum	79 Dollar
8.	Purchase of foundation (for honey molds)	5 sheets 6,000 sum	3 000 000 sum	262 Dollar
9.	Buy frames	5 pcs. 4,000 sums	2 000 000 sum	174 Dollar
10.	Medicines and vitamins for bees	11 200 sum	1 120 000 sum	98 Dollar
11.	Interest expenses on working capital 30% per year		18 000 000	1572 Dollar
	Total		59 620 000 sum	5 200 Dollar
	Total	596 200 sum		52 Dollar

Here is the fixed cost estimate:

Table 3

Calculation of depreciation charges in beekeeping

№	Amortization	100 slots	%
1.	Depreciation for	549 000 sum	6%
2.	Depreciation for each colony	2 416 515 sum	26,41%
3.	Nest	6 184 485 sum	67,59%
	Total	9 150 000 sum	100%

Table 4

Fixed costs in beekeeping

	Жами	15 000 000	per 100 Slots	%
	Fixed Costs			
1.	Permanent Labor		3 000 000	20 %
2.	Interest Costs on Loan		2 550 000	17%
3.	Tools and Equipment		300 000	2%
4.	Depreciation		9 150 000	61%

Total 15,000,000

$$SP = \frac{\text{total costs}}{\text{volume of production}} = \frac{74620000}{1000} = 74620 \text{ sum}$$

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The total cost of obtaining the gross product is equal to the cost of beekeeping and is an important criterion for assessing the success of beekeeping.

Income from the sale of honey worth 100,000 sums per 1 kg is 100,000,000 (one hundred million) sums; The total cost of beekeeping for 100 hives is 74,620,000 sums.

Net income (SD 1) = beekeeper's gross product (GDP 1) - total costs (UX).

$$SD 1 = 100,000,000 - 74,620,000 = 25,380,000 \text{ sums}$$

Based on these calculations, the profitability of beekeeping (P) = SD / GDP.

$$P 1 = 25,380,000 / 100,000,000 = 0.25$$

This means that for every sum spent, 25 cents are received. The cost of 1 kg of honey mined in the mountains (SP) is 74,620 sums.

Certainly, when a beekeeper earns only from selling honey, the calculation results are shown above. The content and purpose of the project was to actively promote in practice that project participants can earn income from several types of beekeeping products, not limited to selling honey. In addition to honey, additional products that can bring additional income are sacs (young bee colonies), royal jelly, propolis, pollen and beeswax. Each of these products can bring significant income to the beekeeper. Table 5 below shows additional revenue figures for these products, taking into account that conservative volume figures were used for each product in the calculations.

Table 5

Sale of additional beekeeping products in season size and income

№	Beekeeping products	Per family (kg)	Per 100 hives (kg)	Price per 1 kg (sum)	Total cost of products from 100 hives (sum)
1.	Propolis	0.1	10	500 000	5 000 000
2.	Wax	0,42	42	50 000	2 100 000
3.	Pollen	2.0	200	150 000	3 000 000
4.	Bags		50	350 000	17 500 000
5.	Mother solution		800	8000	6 400 000
	Total				34 000 000
6.	Bee poison	0,01	1	916 000	916 000

As part of the project, we have developed a simple method for collecting bee venom. The numbers in Table 5 for venom are highlighted in red because it is impossible to sell venom in Uzbekistan, as there are no certified laboratories, we wrote about this in our previous article. The opening of certification laboratories opens the way to the market for beekeeping by-products, and also contributes to the diversification of beekeepers' income. Packages, queen cells are produced and sold, another indicator is formed:

$$GDP 2 = 100,000,000 + 34,000,000 = 134,000,000 \text{ sum};$$

At the same time, total costs remain unchanged. Another income indicator changes other economic indicators of beekeeping.

Net income (SD) = Gross beekeeping product (GDP) - Total costs (UC)

SD 2 = 134,000,000 - 74,620,000 = 59,380,000 sums,

compared to 25,380,000 sums when selling only honey.

Gross profit from one family (hive) increased by 34% and amounted to 1 million 340 thousand sums, instead of 253.8 thousand sums from honey, net profit amounted to 593.8 thousand sum.

The profitability of production will also increase

$P = SD / GNP$

$P = 59,380,000 / 134,000,000 = 0.44$

and now it is 44%, i.e. for every 1 sum spent, the beekeeper earns 44 coins instead of 25 coins only from the sale of honey.

The analysis shows that by diversifying beekeeping products and including in the list of sales not only honey, but also all possible products, without changing the overall cost picture, the beekeeper can increase his net profit by 2.3 times (compared to 44%).

This idea is promoted by the project to improve the economic efficiency of beekeeping, financed by the GEF KGD - to sell all possible beekeeping products to achieve good economic results.

The table 6 shows a comparison of the economic indicators of similar beekeeping farms with different production and sales focuses: one apiary produces and prepares only honey for sale, while another apiary produces and sells honey and other by-products.

Table 6

Comparison of economic indicators of beekeeping for the production and sale of honey and beekeeping for the sale of all bee products

Indications	Bee farm with 100 hives, intended exclusively for honey production, apiary with 100 hives, sale of honey, propolis, bags, royal jelly and wax		1 slot per 100 slots	
	For 1 slot	For 100 slots	For 1slot	For 100 slots
Gross income	10 000 000	100 000 000	13 400 000	134 000 000
Total expenses	746 200	74 620 000	746 200	74 620 000
Net profit	253 800	25 380 000	593 800	59 380 000
Profitability	X	0,25	X	0,44

Conclusions and recommendations. Summarizing the information presented, we can confidently recommend that any beekeeper diversify the beekeeping products received and sold as much as possible in order to increase the economic attractiveness of the business.

Definitely, economic results largely depend on the individual approach of each beekeeper. But the general recommendation of this article remains true - buy and sell not only honey, but also all possible beekeeping products. To get these additional benefits, the beekeeper does not need much additional knowledge. In fact, increasing the educational and professional potential of beekeepers has enormous economic and social benefits for each region and the country as a whole.

To get this additional income, you need to learn the following:

- properly care for bee colonies to get strong families, on the basis of which you can create bags without harm to the family;

- proper creation and development of queen cells;
- collection of royal jelly, wax, pollen, bee bread and other products.

Separately, it is necessary to note the high potential of bee venom production, the market entry of which is currently impossible due to the lack of certification.

The export market of cargo bags also has great potential. Uzbekistan exports up to 311 thousand 2 bags per year. Currently, the largest importer of bags is Russia, where there are on average up to 3 million bee colonies, 20% of which are used in winter, 5% from pesticide poisoning and 5% in season. According to these figures, the Russian market consumes from 900,000 to 1 million bags annually. Agriculture exports more than 70 thousand types of products to Russia. Preparation and production of bags by our beekeepers allow us to use the existing opportunities of the Russian market, as well as the markets of other countries. Increasing the volume of bag exports to 1 million pieces can bring our country more than 30 million dollars. The same applies to other beekeeping products.

On the one hand, there is a market - there is a need and demand that can potentially be satisfied by increasing domestic production. However, the market sets its own conditions, which we often cannot fulfill. The first of these conditions is a guarantee of product safety. For example, Russia, the main importer of our bees, was afraid of an epidemic of bee diseases, which affected almost all of Uzbekistan in the summer of 2022.

In order to fully respond to market demands, the following is necessary:

- delivery without mobile packages compatible with the region standards, which dramatically reduces the number of sick bees.

- improving the quality of beekeeping material and introducing its certification;
- veterinary inspection of all batches of sent parcels and obtaining additional documents

for them;

- put a stamp on each package with information about who, from which beekeeper and breed, and the date of packaging;

- establish direct deliveries without intermediaries;
- delivery of all cars with parcels accompanied by a representative of the supplier.

And this is far from a complete list of consumer demands in the market. This list clearly shows the importance of creating a market infrastructure for beekeeping products.

For the sale of honey, propolis, pollen, royal jelly, special laboratories are needed, the certificates of which confirm the compliance of the product with the standards of the pharmaceutical, perfume and food industries. According to experts, if measures are taken to develop beekeeping, to form the infrastructure of the beekeeping products market, the cultivation of honey and other beekeeping products in the republic can increase significantly. Formation of such infrastructure with the support of the state, as well as large-scale improvement of the professional level of beekeepers can give a great impetus to the development of beekeeping in our country, an increase in the production of beekeeping products. The economic efficiency of individual farms and the entire network increase.

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